

Re-Livestock
RESILIENT FARMING SYSTEMS

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The Re-Livestock on-line tool User manual V1.1

Jo Smith, Ana Tomás, João Palma, MVARC,
Lindsay Whistance, Christian Gossel, Organic Research Centre,
Nicholas Davison, Laurence Smith, University of Reading,

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Introduction

This manual aims to provide users with a complete guide to understanding and using the Re-Livestock Tool. Part 1 lays out the background to the development to the tool, defines the assessment boundaries, describes the data flow through the tool and the subsequent scoring. Part 2 works through each category, describing the questions, which ones are compulsory, used for scoring, and/or feeds into other calculations. Part 3 is a step-by-step guide to using the online tool and discusses how to interpret the results. Detailed data on question dependencies and scoring is provided in an accompanying excel. Eventually this information will be embedded in the tool to ensure transparency of all calculations and scoring.

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Part 1

Background

The Re-Livestock Tool has been developed as part of the European research project 'Re-Livestock' (<https://re-livestock.eu/>). The overall objective of the Re-Livestock project is to evaluate and mobilize the adoption of innovative practices to reduce GHG emissions from livestock farming systems and increase their capacity to deal with potential climate change impacts. Central to achieving this objective are local stakeholder forums and associated innovative case studies which guide and support the co-innovation processes throughout the project. Farms within the case studies are demonstrating innovations in practice, and therefore provide an opportunity for assessing the performance and impacts of such innovations with regards climate change mitigation and adaptation at the farm-level.

To reduce the burden of data collection for the farmers and associated case study facilitators, the aim of the Re-Livestock Tool is to coordinate data requirements and flow by developing a common framework for data collection from case study farms. The framework builds on an existing farm-level sustainability assessment, the Public Goods tool¹. The PG Tool was developed in the UK by the Organic Research Centre as a comprehensive sustainability assessment tool for farming systems that provides a rapid and concise overview of a farm's performance, using a range of environmental, economic, and social indicators. The tool, originally an excel workbook, collects data on farm inputs and outputs, as well as farm practices relating to the delivery of public goods, divided into different areas, or 'spurs'.

Farmers, often with support from farm advisors, complete the assessment, which has been designed to use data or information easily on hand for the farmers and, based on their answers, they are awarded a score for each spur. These scores highlight areas where their farm is performing well as well as potential areas to focus on for improvement. The scores for each spur are presented on a radar diagram while the detailed breakdown for each spur is presented on a bar chart. The PG Tool was initially developed for UK farms; it has since been modified and adapted for use in many UK and pan-European projects, including FP7 (e.g., Sustainable and Low Input Dairying (solidairy.eu)) and Horizon

¹ Gerrard, C.L., Smith, L.G., Padel, S., Pearce, B., Hitchings, R., Measures, M., Cooper, N., (2011), OCIS Public Goods Tool Development, Report for Defra.

projects (e.g., Innovations for Sustainable Sheep and Goat Production in Europe (isage.eu), PATHWAYS for Sustainable Food (pathways-project.com)).

The PG Tool (v3.1) was adapted for the Re-Livestock project to ensure that the data collected reflected the innovations of the case studies plus to gather additional data to feed further analyses within the project (e.g. farm carbon calculation, gender analysis). Other adaptations included modification of existing input to reflect the pan-European scope of the tool (i.e., change in currency units from pounds sterling to Euros, change in some UK-specific terminology) and customisation of the data collection framework to ensure farmers aren't required to fill out questions or categories that are not relevant to them (e.g., questions about land when they are landless units). The final tool consists of 369 questions; of these, 192 have dropdown answers, 10 are multiple choice, 118 are open text or numbers, and 49 are automatically calculated.

The original PG Tool is an excel workbook consisting of 17 sheets; while an excellent format for research purposes and for allowing transparency of calculations and scoring, the excel is not very user-friendly and is prone to human errors (e.g., missing data entries). It was decided that the Re-Livestock data collection platform should be an online platform to ease and standardise data collection across the many countries and case studies, and to provide a legacy of the project that would be available, open access, for anyone to use. To enable to efficient construction of the Re-Livestock data collection platform, the original PG Tool v3.1 excel was first transformed into an online version (<https://www.organicresearchcentre.com/PG-Tool/>), available in github and prepared for versioning control (<https://github.com/orgs/organicresearchcentre/repositories>). The next step was to modify this version to integrate the revised and new questions and data points and to transform the branding in line with the Re-Livestock design.

The first draft of the Re-Livestock data collection platform was tested internally by the Task team, using real farm data collected previously using the PG Tool. This identified initial bugs and errors in the tool. A second round of testing was then carried out by volunteers from the case study facilitators to enable broader feedback on errors and potential improvements. The final version was launched in November 2023.

Assessment boundaries

The assessment covers a 12-month period; this can be the 12-month period that makes the most sense for the farm, e.g. the farming year, financial year or calendar year. It is important that whatever is chosen is used consistently throughout the assessment so that all data is covering the same period.

The assessment and calculations such as nutrient balances are on a farm-gate basis, i.e. only capturing products entering and leaving the farm. For example, if crops grown on the farm are fed to livestock on the farm, this 'feed' and internal cycling of nutrients and energy would not be directly captured but would be evident in the nutrient balance.

The assessment is applied to a farm business; for example, if land is rented out for grazing by another farmer, the land area and rental income is included in the assessment, but data on the livestock (owned by another farm business) is not collected.

Data flow

The initial data collection sheet is the heart of the assessment, collecting data relating to area of crops grown, harvested and exported, area of temporary and permanent pasture, livestock numbers, imports and exports, imports and exports of seed, feed, straw and fertilisers, and areas of woodland and hedgerow. These data feed into several of the calculations within the assessment including NPK balance, and energy benchmarking (Figure 1). More detailed data on livestock performance are also collected to feed into a farm carbon calculation (calculation not currently included in the assessment but carried out externally). Additional data on fuel use, water use, employment and farm income and costs are collected and used to inform scoring of the individual spurs (Figure 1).

Re-Livestock Tool Flowchart

* Calculated parameters use standard data derived from research reports, management handbooks, Government statistics etc.

Figure 1. Data flow within the Re-Livestock assessment

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Scoring approach

Scores are given to each question and averaged to give a score for the activities within each spur. Most questions are scored on a scale of 1 (poor performance) to 5 (best performance). An N/A option is available for many questions; this is not included in the scores. The overall score for each spur is then an average of the activities within that category (e.g. Table 1). There are no weightings given to any of the scores, but there is, in fact, a hidden weighting or bias because of the uneven number of questions per activity.

Table 1. Calculations of an example of scoring in one category

Question	Score	Activity	Score	Spur	Score
Soil organic matter	5	Soil analysis	5	Soil Management	$= 5 + 3.4 + 3.3 = 3.9$
Woody plants in arable area	3	Soil management	$= (3+2+3+5+4)/5 = 3.4$		
% arable land left bare	2				
% fertility building in rotation	3				
Steps to enhance SOM (8 options)	5				
Actions to avoid soil compaction (4 options)	4				
Sheet erosion % cover	3	Soil erosion	$= (3+4+3+5+2+2+4)/7 = 3.3$		
Rill erosion % cover	4				
Gully erosion % cover	3				
Ponding % cover	5				
Capping of soil surface % cover	2				
Wind erosion % cover	2				
Other soil damage % cover	4				

Where there is relevant research evidence or benchmarking data available, scoring is based on this. Where there is no existing data, scoring for many questions inherited from the PG Tool is based on expert knowledge, and for new questions, on the judgement of the tool's authors in consultation with Re-Livestock partners.

Part 2

Initial data

The initial data page is the heart of the assessment, collecting data relating to area of crops grown, harvested and exported, area of temporary and permanent pasture, livestock numbers, imports and exports, imports and exports of seed, feed, straw and fertilisers, and areas of woodland and hedgerow. These data feed into several of the calculations within the assessment including the NPK balance and energy benchmarking. Standard data on NPK and energy (MJ) contents of crops, livestock, seed, feed and fertilisers are sourced from a range of references including Chamberlain and Wilkinson², the EASI tool³ and Watson et al⁴. See sections 2.6 and 2.8 for more details of the calculations. The initial Farm Information data are not used for scoring but are collected to provide context for subsequent analyses.

A note on dependencies

The full assessment contains over 300 questions. To reduce the burden on farmers filling out the assessment, irrelevant sections and questions are filtered out, depending on the type of farm. Many of these 'dependencies' are related to data that are added to the initial data page e.g.:

Q1.0.6 "Farming System?"

→ "Indoor only/landless" – Only the spurs Water Management, Fertiliser Management, Energy and Carbon, Food Security, Agricultural Systems Diversity, Social Capital, Economic data and Farm Business Resilience are shown and need to be completed.

→ "Includes land" – if livestock are then added, all 13 spurs are then shown and need to be included. If the farm has no livestock, the Animal Health & Welfare spur is not shown.

The type of livestock added to Q1.6 will then determine which species-specific questions are shown in the Animal Health & Welfare spur. Questions with dependencies are indicated with a *. For details of all dependencies, please refer to Section 4.

Data for a Carbon Calculation

As part of the Re-Livestock project, farm carbon calculations will be carried out, using data collected in this Re-Livestock assessment. Therefore, some data are collected specifically for this purpose. The carbon calculations will be carried out externally to the assessment, using the AgreCalc calculator (<https://www.agrecalc.com/>).

² Chamberlain, A.T. and Wilkinson, J.M. (1996) Feeding the Dairy Cow. Chalcombe Publications ISBN 0948617322

³ Smith, L. and Woodward, L. (2010) Environmental benchmarking and sustainability assessment for organic agriculture, ORC Bulletin

⁴ Watson, C., Topp, K., Stockdale, L. (2010), A Guide to Nutrient Budgeting on Organic Farms, Institute of Organic Training and Advice

Table 2. Questions in the Initial data page. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Farm information			
Farm name	Y	N	
What country are you based?	Y	N	
Language?	Y	N	
What is your currency?	Y	N	Used in Economics spur calculations
What's the current exchange rate?*	Y	N	Used in Economics spur calculations
Dates covered	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
Farming system?	Y	N	
Which is your farm business type?	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
Please, specify other business type*	Y	N	
Primarily the farm owner, or tenant?	Y	N	
Please, specify other type of ownership*	Y	N	
Are there additional co-operative or companies involved in this farm?	Y	N	
Gender of farmer	Y	N	Used for Re-Livestock gender task
Age of farmer	Y	N	
Education level of farmer	Y	N	
Who is working on the farm?	Y	N	Used for Re-Livestock gender task
Dominant soil type*	Y	N	
Annual rainfall*	Y	N	
Altitude	Y	N	
Are you organic/in conversion?	Y	N	
Number of years/months since organic conversion started*	Y	N	
Number of years/months fully organic*	N	N	
What is the level of agri-environmental participation?	N	N	
Do you implement some innovative approach in your farm?	Y	N	
Please, describe the innovation succinctly*	Y	N	
Crops*			

Crop type	N	N	Used in NPK and Energy ratio calculations and farm carbon calculation
Crop area*	Y	N	Used to calculate total yield, total arable area and farm carbon calculation
Marketable yield*	Y	N	Used to calculate total yield
Total yield*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from Area and Marketable yield Used for farm carbon calculation
Yield exported*	Y	N	Used in NPK and Energy ratio calculations and farm carbon calculation
Forage crop type	N	N	Used in N calculation and farm carbon calculation
Forage crop area*	Y	N	Used in N calculation, total arable area and farm carbon calculation
Temporary pasture type	N	N	Used in N calculation
Temporary pasture area*	Y	N	Used in N calculation and total arable area calculation and farm carbon calculation Used in Agri-environmental management spur
Temporary pasture – age since establishment*	Y	N	Used in N calculation and farm carbon calculation
Permanent pasture type	N	N	Used in N calculation and farm carbon calculation
Permanent pasture area*	Y	N	Used in N calculation, total grassland area calculation and farm carbon calculation Used in Agri-environmental management spur
Permanent pasture – age since establishment*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
Moorland area	N	N	Used to calculate total grassland area Used in farm carbon calculation
Other (e.g. game cover) area	N	N	Used to calculate total grassland area Used in farm carbon calculation
Ponds and watercourses area	N	N	Used to calculate total other land area Used in farm carbon calculation
Designated non cropped nature reserve land / agri-environmental land (e.g field margins, wild bird mixtures)	N	N	Used to calculate total other land area Used in farm carbon calculation
Farm Woodland and Agroforestry*			
Type, area and average age of Farm Woodland	N	N	Used to calculate total woodland area and farm carbon calculation
Yield exported	N	N	Used to calculate energy ratio Used in farm carbon calculation
Other standing trees (incl. in field)	N	N	Used in farm carbon calculation

Typical area under crown for other standing trees (incl. in field)	N	N	
Total hedges under 30 years	N	N	
Total hedges over 30 years	N	N	
Total hedges	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total hedges under + over 30 years
Do you manage hedges for woodfuel?	N	N	
Total length of hedgerow managed for fuel*	N	N	
Woodfuel yield (tonnes per km of hedgerow)*	N	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
Total woodfuel yield*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from length of hedges managed for woodfuel and woodfuel yield
Woodfuel yield exported*	N	N	Used to calculate energy ratio Used in farm carbon calculation
Land use			
Other non agricultural land	N	N	Used to calculate total other land area Used in farm carbon calculation
Built up land including roads	N	N	Used to calculate total built up land area farm carbon calculation
Total arable area	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from crop, forage crop and temporary pasture area Used to calculate energy benchmarks
Total grass (permanent) area	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from permanent pasture, moorland and other grassland area
Total UAA (utilisable agricultural area)	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total arable and total grassland area Used for calculations of NPK balance, livestock stocking rates, atmospheric N deposition and farm carbon calculation
Total woodland area	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total of different woodland types area
Other land	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total ponds, non-cropped and other non-agricultural area
Total built-up land	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total built-up land area
Total area	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total UAA, woodland, grassland and built up land area

Imported Seeds and Feeds			
Seed type	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance and energy ratio Used in farm carbon calculation
Seed Import & Export*	Y	N	
Feed type	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance and energy ratio U Used in farm carbon calculation
Feed Import & Export*	Y	N	
New feed – NPK & Energy*	Y	N	
Bedding - Arable straw - Import & Export	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance and energy ratio Used in farm carbon calculation
Bedding - Sawdust – Import & Export	N	N	
Bedding - Forest residue/woodchip – Import & Export	N	N	
Organic and inorganic fertiliser			
Organic fertiliser type	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance Used in farm carbon calculation
Organic fertiliser Import & export*	Y	N	
New organic fertiliser – NPK*	Y	N	
Inorganic fertiliser type	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance Used in farm carbon calculation
Inorganic fertiliser Import*	Y	N	
New inorganic fertiliser – NPK*	Y	N	
Livestock			
Livestock type	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance, energy ratios and stocking densities farm carbon calculation
Average no. of animals held on farm over 12 month period*	Y	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance, energy ratios and stocking densities Used in farm carbon calculation
Typical average liveweight*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated based on livestock type
Average liveweight*	Y	N	Used for farm carbon calculation
Import*	Y	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance, Used in farm carbon calculation
Export (excluding deaths)*	Y	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance, energy ratios.
Deaths*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
Slaughter or sale age*	Y	N	
What is your cow's average age at first calving?*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation

What % of your breeding cows produce calves?*	Y	N	
What is your average calf birthweight?*	Y	N	
What is the average liveweight at weaning for your sheep?*	Y	N	
What is the liveweight at one year or at slaughter if slaughtered before one year for your sheep?*	Y	N	
What is the average number of piglets born per litter?*	Y	N	
What is the average number of piglets reared per litter?*	Y	N	
What is the average number of litters per sow per year?*	Y	N	
What percentage of sheep lambing were singles?*	Y	N	
What percentage of sheep lambing were twins?*	Y	N	
What percentage of sheep lambing were triplets?*	Y	N	
Who is taking decisions for livestock management issues?	Y	N	Used for Re-Livestock gender task
Livestock product type	N	N	Used for calculations of NPK balance, energy ratios.
Livestock product Import & Export*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
New livestock product NPK*	Y	N	
Fat and protein content in milk*	Y	N	Used for calculations of energy ratios.

Soil management

This spur only appears if the farm assessed has land. If the farm is a landless system (e.g. indoor pigs), this spur will not appear.

Table 3. Questions in the Soil management spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Soil analysis			
If you regularly measure soil organic matter, on average, are you increasing, decreasing or maintaining Soil Organic Matter levels across your farm?	Y	Y	N
Soil management			
Do you have woody plants (trees, hedges, shrubs) in your arable area?*	Y	Y	N
What % of arable land is left bare over the winter?*	Y	Y	N
What % of your crop rotation is fertility building?*	Y	Y	N
Which steps do you take to enhance soil biology/soil organic matter? (8 options)	Y	Y	N
Which of the following actions do you take to avoid soil compaction? (4 options)	Y	Y	N
Soil erosion			
% of land with Sheet erosion	Y	Y	N
% of land with Rill erosion	Y	Y	N
% of land with Gully erosion	Y	Y	N
% of land with Ponding	Y	Y	N
% of land with Capping of soil surface	Y	Y	N
% of land with Wind erosion	Y	Y	N
% of land with Other soil erosion	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur*	N	N	N

Agri-environmental management

This spur only appears if the farm assessed has land. If the farm is a landless system (e.g. indoor pigs), this spur will not appear.

Table 4. Questions in the Agri-environmental management spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Agri-environmental participation			
How many environmental management options do you undertake on your farm?	Y	Y	N
Conservation plan			
Do you have a whole farm written voluntary conservation plan and/or are you part of a farmland conservation organisation (e.g. LEAF in the UK)?	Y	Y	N
3rd party endorsement			
Have you received any 3rd party endorsement for your biodiversity activities (including awards but excluding certifications such as Organic)	Y	Y	N
Habitat			
Percentage of land which is permanent pasture*	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from Initial data (area of permanent pasture and total farm area)
Percentage of permanent pasture managed as low input or very low input*	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from Initial data (area of permanent pasture)
What percentage of your arable area contains buffer strips / field margins?*	Y	Y	N
What percentage of your arable land is managed as cover for wild birds, bees, other pollinators, etc?*	Y	Y	N
How much of your woodland consists of native tree species?*	Y	Y	N
To what extent do you manage farm woodland?*	Y	Y	N
Do you allow woodland grazing?*	Y	Y	N
Do you protect in-field trees?	Y	Y	N
Do you have wildlife habitats (e.g. wet grassland) or are you restoring and/or establishing wildlife habitats on your land? If so, how much land is a wildlife habitat as a percentage of total land area?	Y	Y	N
Are you monitoring habitats, e.g. monitoring soil condition, vegetation cover, biodiversity? And are you maintaining them as necessary to keep them in good condition, if so how regularly?	Y	Y	N
Farmland indicator species			
How many of these indicator species have you seen on your farm?	Y	Y	N
Livestock*			
What is the stocking rate on the farm?*	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated From Initial data (total UAA, Nr animals, and livestock type)
Does your animal breed provide environmental benefits when compared to typical species used in conventional farming (e.g. does it have lower methane emissions, biodiversity benefits through grazing, etc)?*	Y	Y	N
Please, specify which environmental benefits it provides.*	Y	N	N
Management of arable land*			
What is the average size of your arable fields?*	Y	Y	N
Management of pastureland*			

What percentage of permanent grassland is unfertilised?*	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from Initial data (permanent grassland type and area)
What percentage of your permanent pasture is regarded as having high nature values (from authorities or other experts)?*	Y	Y	N
What percentage of the permanent pasture fields is covered by bushes and trees?*	Y	Y	N
Herbicide and other pesticide use			
Do you use herbicides, insecticides, fungicides or other products (e.g. straw shorteners)? These include organic/natural alternatives.	Y	Y	N
When using such products do you avoid ponds, hedgerows, woodland, rough grazing and species-rich grassland?*	Y	Y	N
When using pesticides/other control measures do you consider impact on beneficial species?*	Y	Y	N
When using pesticides/other control measures, how do you decide on amounts to use?*	Y	Y	N
How often do you calibrate and maintain the sprayer?*	Y	Y	N
Do you take action to prevent contamination of water courses, lakes and ponds?*	Y	Y	N
Do you consider the safety of bees when selecting which pesticides to use?*	Y	Y	N
Do you consider the safety of bees by spraying late in the evening when they are not working and by not spraying flowering plants?*	Y	Y	N
Do you consider the safety of birds when using dressed seeds or pesticides in granular/pellet form by ensuring that they do not remain on the soil surface but are fully incorporated?*	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur.*	N	N	N

Landscape and Heritage Features

This spur only appears if the farm assessed has land. If the farm is a landless system (e.g. indoor pigs), this spur will not appear.

Table 5. Questions in the Landscape and Heritage Features spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Historic features			
Are there historic features present on the farm (including archaeological features, traditional buildings, listed monuments)?	Y	N	N
How much maintenance/care do you give them?*	Y	Y	N
What sort of condition are they in?*	Y	Y	N
Landscape features			
How much of the land is administratively regarded as less favoured area?	Y	Y	N
Management of boundaries			
Do you have high environmental value boundaries on your farm?	Y	Y	N
How many hedgerow trees per 100m do you have on the farm?*	Y	Y	N
Are you taking action to restore boundary features (e.g. high nature value walls, ditches, dykes)?*	Y	Y	N
Genetic heritage*			
Do you farm any rare breeds of livestock?*	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur.*	N	N	N

Water management

Table 6. Questions in the Water management spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Implementation of measures to minimise water pollution and maximise water efficiency			
What intensity of action(s) is/are being taken for water resource protection?	Y	Y	
Water harvesting			
How much of the water you use on farm is recycled?	Y	Y	
Water usage*			
How much water do you use annually on livestock for drinking?*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
How much water do you use annually for purposes other than livestock drinking (e.g. cleaning)?*	Y	N	
Irrigation			
What % of Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) is irrigated using mains or abstracted water?	Y	Y	
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur.	N	N	

NPK budget

This spur only appears if the farm assessed has land. If the farm is a landless system (e.g. indoor pigs), this spur will not appear.

Farm gate NPK balance and input/output ratio

The farm-gate NPK ratios are automatically calculated based on data entered in the Initial data page of the imports and exports of crops, livestock and livestock products, seeds, feeds, bedding and fertilisers and their associated NPK contents taken from standard data (Figure 11). The balance is presented as kg/ha and the following guidance given on interpretation of the results (Figure 12). The data is also presented as a ratio of output to inputs. Below the farm-gate balance, the detail is shown regarding the inputs and outputs of NPK for the different crops grown, livestock and livestock products, N fixation in any grassland with clover, inputs and outputs of fertilisers, feeds and seeds.

Scoring for this spur is based on surpluses or deficits of NPK, using the scale Figure 12 to assign scores from 1 for 'Poor/very poor' to 5 for 'Excellent/very good'. The score is based on Guide to Nutrient Budgeting ([IOTA, 2015](#))⁵. The final score for NPK balance is an average of the scores for N, P and K.

GUIDANCE ON NPK BALANCE			
Nitrogen kg/ha	Sustainability	Phosphorus and Potassium kg/ha	Sustainability
0-50 kg/ha:	Excellent - Very good	Surplus/defecit less than 5 kg/ha:	Very good - Excellent
50-70 kg/ha:	Very good - good	Surplus/defecit of greater than 5kg/ha, less than 10kg/ha:	Average - Good
70-90 kg/ha:	Good - Average	Surplus/defecit of greater than 10 kg/ha:	Poor - very poor
90-110 kg/ha	Average - Poor		
110-130 kg/ha plus+	Poor - very poor		

Figure 12. Guidance on NPK balance

⁵ A Guide to Nutrient Budgeting on Organic Farms. Creator(s): Watson, Christine; Topp, Cairistiona F E and Stockdale, Elizabeth. Issuing Organisation(s): IOTA - Institute of Organic Training and Advice. Technical Leaflet, no. 6. (2010)

Fertiliser management

Table 7. Questions in the Fertiliser management spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Fertiliser management and application*			
How often are fertiliser spreaders inspected and maintained?*	Y	Y	N
How regularly are fertiliser application rates checked during the growing / spreading season?*	Y	Y	N
At what time(s) of year do you spread chemical nitrogen fertilisers?*	Y	Y	N
Nutrient planning*			
How do you determine the level of nutrient application for crops and pasture?*	Y	Y	N
How regularly do you monitor/record levels of major nutrients (e.g. P (phosphorus), K (potassium), Mg (magnesium), Ca (calcium), S (sulphur)) in the soil?*	Y	Y	N
To what extent are staff trained in the accurate/efficient application of nutrients to crops and pasture?*	Y	Y	N
Do you know the N (nitrogen), P (phosphorus), K (potassium) content of organic manures/composts applied?*	Y	Y	Used in farm carbon calculation
Manure management*			
What is the % of time at pasture per livestock type*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
What is the % of time at liquid slurry per livestock type*	Y	N	
What is the % of time at pit storage (slats) per livestock type*	Y	N	
What is the % of time at solid storage (FYM) per livestock type*	Y	N	
What is the % of time at deep bedding (retained > 1 year) per livestock type*	Y	N	
Total % of time housed per livestock type*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from % time in different housing types
Total % of time per livestock type*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total time at pasture and housed
How long is liquid slurry stored for?*	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
How long is solid storage (FYM) stored for?*	Y	N	
How long is pit storage (slats) stored for?*	Y	N	
How long is deep bedding (retained > 1 year) stored for?*	Y	N	
How do you predominantly store/manage manure on farm?*	Y	Y	N
How do you predominantly store slurry?*	Y	Y	N
What is the condition of the floor for your slurry storage system?*	Y	Y	N
How many months storage capacity do you have for slurry/dirty water?*	Y	Y	N
How often do you completely empty and inspect manure/slurry storage facilities?*	Y	Y	N
Farm waste			
Annual on-farm waste plastic/packaging generation?	Y	N	Used in farm carbon calculation
What percentage of farm waste (e.g. plastics, metals, timber etc) is recycled?	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			

Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade-offs for this spur.*	N	N	N
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Energy and carbon

Table 8. Questions in the Energy and carbon spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Fuel use			
Fuel Type	Y	N	Used to calculate energy benchmarks and ratios and renewable energy total Used for farm carbon calculations
Amount of fuel	Y	N	
Own fuel use – Arable*	Y	N	
Own fuel use – Horticulture*	Y	N	
Own fuel use - Beef cattle and Sheep*	Y	N	
Own fuel use - Dairy cattle*	Y	N	
Own fuel use – Pigs*	Y	N	
Own fuel use - Poultry – Broilers*	Y	N	
Own fuel use - Poultry – Layers*	Y	N	
Biomass production*	Y	N	
Own fuel use - Total	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from fuel type and amount
Contractor type	N	N	Used to calculate energy benchmarks and ratios Used for farm carbon calculations
Amount of contractor's fuel use*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use – Arable*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use – Horticulture*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use - Beef cattle and Sheep*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use - Dairy cattle*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use – Pigs*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use - Poultry – Broilers*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use - Poultry – Layers*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use - Biomass production*	Y	N	
Contractor's fuel use - Total	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from contractor type and amount
Arable - total farm fuel use*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total arable area, own fuel use and amount, contractor fuel use and amount
Arable - farm fuel use per hectare*		N	Calculated from total arable area and total arable energy use
Arable – benchmark*		N	Calculated from total arable area and standard industry benchmark data
Arable - % of benchmark*		Y	Calculated from arable energy per ha and arable benchmark
Beef and Sheep - total farm fuel use*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from nr animals, own fuel use and amount, contractor fuel use and amount
Beef and Sheep - farm fuel use per head*		N	Calculated from nr animals and total beef/sheep energy use
Beef and Sheep – benchmark*		N	Calculated from nr animals and standard industry benchmark data
Beef and Sheep - % of benchmark*		Y	Calculated from beef/sheep energy per head and beef/sheep benchmark

Dairy - total farm fuel use*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from nr animals, own fuel use and amount, contractor fuel use and amount
Dairy - farm fuel use per head*		N	Calculated from nr animals and total dairy energy use
Dairy – benchmark*		N	Calculated from nr animals and standard industry benchmark data
Dairy - % of benchmark*		Y	Calculated from dairy energy per head and dairy benchmark
Pig - total farm fuel use*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from nr animals, own fuel use and amount, contractor fuel use and amount
Pig - farm fuel use per head*		N	Calculated from nr animals and total pig energy use
Pig – benchmark*		N	Calculated from nr animals and standard industry benchmark data
Pig - % of benchmark*		Y	Calculated from pig energy per head and pig benchmark
Poultry - Layers - total farm fuel use*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from nr animals, own fuel use and amount, contractor fuel use and amount
Poultry - Layers - farm fuel use per head*		N	Calculated from nr animals and total layers energy use
Poultry - Layers – benchmark*		N	Calculated from nr animals and standard industry benchmark data
Poultry - Layers - % of benchmark*		Y	Calculated from layers energy per head and layers benchmark
Poultry - Broilers - total farm fuel use*	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from nr animals, own fuel use and amount, contractor fuel use and amount
Poultry - Broilers - farm fuel use per head*		N	Calculated from nr animals and total broilers energy use
Poultry - Broilers – benchmark*		N	Calculated from nr animals and standard industry benchmark data
Poultry - Broilers - % of benchmark*		Y	Calculated from broilers energy per head and broilers benchmark
Renewable energy			
Total farm direct energy use	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from arable, beef/sheep, dairy, pigs, broilers energy use Used for farm carbon calculations
Total farm renewable energy use		N	Calculated from fuel type (woodfuel and renewable electricity) Used for farm carbon calculations
Percent renewable		Y	Calculated from total farm direct energy use and total renewable energy use
Do you produce energy and do you export energy off farm (e.g. supplying solar energy to the grid, selling wood chip to neighbours)?	Y	Y	N
Renewable electricity produced from wind/solar PV/hydro/biogas*	Y	N	Used to calculate total renewable energy produced Used for farm carbon calculations

Total renewable electricity produced	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from renewable energy produced Used for farm carbon calculations
Energy ratio			
Arable energy ratio	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from crop, feed and bedding exports, and imported energy (MJ) from arable energy use
Beef/sheep energy ratio		Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from livestock and livestock products exports, and imported energy (MJ) from beef/sheep energy use
Dairy cattle energy ratio		Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from livestock and livestock products exports, and imported energy (MJ) from dairy energy use
Pig energy ratio		Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from livestock and livestock products exports, and imported energy (MJ) from pig energy use
Poultry – layers energy ratio		Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from livestock and livestock products exports, and imported energy (MJ) from layers energy use
Poultry – broilers energy ratio		Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from livestock and livestock products exports, and imported energy (MJ) from broilers energy use
Biomass energy ratio		Y	Calculated from exported energy (MJ) from woodland and hedges, and imported energy (MJ) from biomass energy use
Energy saving options			
Do you monitor/record on-farm energy use?	Y	Y	N
Energy consumption from manufacturing fertiliser*			
Are fertilisers produced with Best Available Techniques (BAT)?*	Y	Y	N
Greenhouse gases			
Have you completed a carbon calculation and are you acting on recommendations?	Y	Y	N
How many agri-environment options relevant to C sequestration do you have on the farm?	Y	Y	N
Are you taking any additional measures to reduce GHGs (i.e. using feed additives to reduce methane etc)?	Y	Y	N
Please, specify which additional measures you are taking.*	Y	N	N
Land use change*			

Have you converted woodland or grassland to arable in the last 20 years? How many hectares?*	N	Y	% change calculated from total woodland and grassland area
Have you converted arable land to permanent grassland or woodland in the last 20 years? How many hectares?*	N	Y	% change calculated from total arable area
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur*	N	N	N

Fossil fuel use by enterprise compared to benchmark

To benchmark fuel use per enterprise, farmers are asked to enter the amount of the different fuel types (diesel, electricity (including renewable electricity, heating oil, gas, woodfuel) used over the last 12 months, divided between enterprises, expressed as a percentage. They are asked to account for contractors separately, entering the amount of contract labour over the last 12 months, divided by enterprise, expressed as a percentage. Total fuel use (including contractors) per enterprise is converted to MegaJoules and this is compared with benchmark figures from a sample of 950 farms⁶.

Food security

Table 9. Questions in the Food security spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Total productivity			
How would you describe your yield compared with average yields for similar types of farm?	Y	Y	N
Number of products from the farm	Y	Y	N
Local food			
Approximately what percentage of your produce (by weight) is sold to local sales (< 10miles / < 16km)/county sales/regional sales/national sales/international sales	Y	N	N
Total percentage of local food sales (local, county and regional sales)	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from % products sold locally/regionally/nationally/internationally
3rd party endorsement			
Have you received any 3rd party endorsement for for food quality/local food production (including awards but excluding certifications)?	Y	Y	N
Food quality certification and traceability			
What level of food quality certification do you have?	Y	Y	N
Are animals correctly identified and is product traceability ensured through animal identification tags (e.g. ear tags, ID tattoo)?*	Y	Y	N

⁶ CALU & ADAS (2007) *Managing Energy and Carbon: The farmer's guide to energy audits*

Does the farm produce Produce of Designated Origin (PDO), Protected Geographic Status (PGS) or Traditional Specialities Guaranteed (TSG) or equivalent?	Y	Y	N
Production of fresh produce			
Hectares of farm used to grow fruit, roots and other vegetables*	Y		N
What percentage (by weight) of your crops would you estimate goes for human consumption rather than animal consumption?*	Y		N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur.*	N	N	N

Agricultural systems diversity

Table 10. Questions in the Agricultural systems diversity spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsor y?	Scored ?	Used calculations? in
Rotational and varietal diversity*			
How diverse is the crop rotation on your farm in terms of numbers of crop types?*	Y	Y	N
How many species/varieties do you grow in total for: cereals/ fodder crops/ grain legume and oilseeds/ vegetables/ forage/ green manures/leys/temporary pasture/ permanent pasture?*	N	Y	Used to calculate total number of species/varieties
How many species/varieties do you grow in total?*	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from sum of all crop species/varieties
Livestock diversity*			
How diverse is the livestock system on the farm with regard to numbers of breeds/crossbreeds of dairy cattle/ beef cattle/ sheep/ pigs/ poultry?*	Y	Y	Used to calculate total number of species/varieties
Total number of livestock breeds/crossbreeds*	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from sum of breeds/crossbreeds of livestock
Name the breeds/crossbreeds*	Y	N	N
Marketing outlets			
Through how many outlets do you market your produce?	Y	Y	N
How many of these routes are local markets (e.g. farm shop, local delivery, local market, local shops)?	Y	Y	N
Do you sell produce direct to customers on-farm?	Y	Y	N
Would you be open to direct sales?	Y	Y	N
To what extent do you provide public access to your animals?	Y	Y	N
On farm processing			
Do you process on farm products?	Y	Y	N
How many different products do you process on farm or off-farm with local partnerships/businesses?*	Y	Y	N
Please list product/s and rough quantity over the year.*	Y	N	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade-offs for this spur.*	N	N	N

Social capital

Table 11. Questions in the Social capital spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsor y?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Employment			
How many staff do you employ? (including yourself):			
Casual (combined total hours of all casual staff)	N	Y	Used to calculate FTE/ha using total UAA Used to calculate nr injuries/FTE
Long term (excluding family)	N	Y	
Family labour	N	Y	
What impact does your innovation have on the wages you can provide staff?*	Y	N	N
Work-life balance*			
How does your innovation impact the amount of working hours/labour requirements?*	Y	Y	N
Local employment			
Of your total workforce during the last five years, what proportion was short-term employed or hired?	Y	Y	N
Of your short-term workforce during the last five years, what proportion was from the same municipality as your farm?	Y	Y	N
Of your long-term workforce during the last five years, what proportion was from the same municipality as your farm?	Y	Y	N
Of your total workforce during the last five years, what proportion was from your family?	Y	Y	N
Skills and knowledge			
How many training days have staff (including the farmer) had per year in total - number of days per person?			
Casual	N	Y	N
Long term (including family)*	Y	Y	N
How well qualified are your staff (including yourself)? (by experience and/or courses/certification)	Y	Y	N
Community engagement			
How many visitor events do you have per year?	Y	Y	N
Do you use any of the means of communication listed below?	N	Y	N
How many visitors come through the farm gate?	Y	Y	N
Have you received any awards for staff welfare/community engagement?	Y	Y	N
Do you have any evidence of consumer satisfaction? Highlight all that apply.			
Yes, verbal feedback - public	Y	N	Used to calculate total nr of positive feedback
Yes, written feedback - public	Y	N	
Yes, verbal feedback - private	Y	N	
Yes, written feedback - private	Y	N	
Yes, customers return to farm	Y	N	
Other	Y	N	
If you selected 'Other', please specify*	N	N	N
Total number of positive feedback (hidden)	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from nr of positive feedback
Which feedback is most important to you?	Y	N	N

Thinking about your farming innovation, to what extent do you feel part of a community of practice?*	Y	Y	N
Thinking about your innovation and/or case study community, what level of involvement/influence do you feel you have on shaping farming practices?*	Y	Y	N
Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives and accreditations			
Are you accredited by a corporate social accreditation scheme (e.g. 'Investors in People' in the UK)?	Y	Y	N
Are you a member of an ethical trade scheme?	Y	Y	N
Public access			
How much access do you provide?	Y	Y	N
Do you maintain areas of public access?	Y	Y	N
Do you promote public access?	Y	Y	N
Human health issues			
Have you carried out a risk assessment of hazardous substances on your farm?	Y	Y	N
How rigorously is health and safety enforced on the farm? ie: how much training and/or risk assessment is provided	Y	Y	N
How is the working atmosphere at your farm?	Y	Y	N
How onerous (tough) is the workload on your farm?	Y	Y	N
Do you share workload or equipment with neighbouring farmers?	Y	Y	N
Are you happy with the amount of holiday period you can take over a year?	Y	Y	N
Does your innovation improve the quality of the food?*	Y	Y	N
Health and safety workers			
How many persons got an injury (or injuries) when working in your company during the last year?	Y	N	Used to calculate nr injuries/FTE
Number of injured persons per full time worker	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated by number FTE and nr injuries
Influence on society			
Thinking about your farming innovation when compared to conventional practices, what impact do you think you are having on society (such as providing environmental and social benefits, or aiding sustainable development)?*	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur*	N	N	N

Economic data

Table 12. Questions in the Economic data spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory ?	Scored ?	Used calculations? in
Income			
Sales of livestock	N	N	Used to calculate total income (sum of receipts)
Annual sales of livestock products	N	N	
Crop and pasture sales	N	N	
Income from other farm-related activities	N	N	
Farmhouse consumption	N	N	
Government payments and support	N	N	
Other income	N	N	
Please, specify other income*	Y	N	Calculated from sum of all income Used to calculate Farm Net Income and Reliance on subsidies (in Farm Business Resilience)
Sum of receipts	Auto-calculated	N	
Costs			
Aggregated costs	N	N	Used to calculate total costs (sum of costs)
Feedstuffs	N	N	
Veterinarian	N	N	
Medicines	N	N	
Processing	N	N	
Other costs	N	N	
Please, specify other costs	N	N	
Seeds	N	N	
Fertilisers	N	N	
Forestry	N	N	
Labour costs (not including salary to owners)	N	N	
Machinery costs (including rental and maintenance)	N	N	
Farming overheads (upkeep of land and buildings, including energy, water and administration costs)	N	N	
Rents paid	N	N	
Depreciation	N	N	
Other costs	N	N	Calculated from sum of all costs Used to calculate Farm Net Income
Please, specify other costs*	Y	N	
Sum of costs	Auto-calculated	N	
Assets			
Assets (cash, stock value, machinery, buildings, etc)	N	N	Used to calculate owner equity
Liabilities, both short and long term	N	N	
Owner equity/Farm Net Worth	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from assets and liabilities Used to calculate financial solidity (in Farm Business Resilience)

Own input			
Company owner(s) labour time	N	N	Used to calculate net result to company owners labour/h, local currency
Key figures			
Farm Net Income	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from total income and total costs Used to calculate net result to company owners labour/h, local currency
Extra key figures			
Net result to company owner(s) labour/h, local currency	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from company owner(s) labour time and Farm Net Income
Net result to company owner(s) labour/h, €	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from net result to company owner(s) labour/h, local currency, Farm info currency and exchange rate
Comparison national net, %	Auto-calculated	N	Compared with national and EU figures on labour costs
Comparison EU net, PPP, %	Auto-calculated	N	
Impact of innovation*			
To what extent does your innovation make you more or less susceptible to cost increases and supply chain shocks?*	Y	Y	N
How do the initial costs for your innovative farming compare to conventional farming (i.e. higher due to extra housing/equipment, or lower due to reduced housing/equipment etc)?*	Y	Y	N
How do the profit margins with your innovation compare to conventional farming (i.e. net impacts from increased/reduced annual costs, and increased/reduced annual revenues)?*	Y	Y	N
Please, specify why the innovation has that impact on profit margins?*	Y	N	N
Are there any subsidies you receive related to your innovation?*	Y	Y	N
Please, specify which subsidies.*	Y	N	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur*	N	N	N

Farm business resilience

Table 13. Questions in the Farm business resilience spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory ?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Financial viability			
Do you feel like you receive a fair price for your products?	Y	Y	N
Do you feel like the price you receive covers the costs you make for the products?	Y	Y	N
How have your net assets (total assets less total liabilities) changed in the last year?	Y	Y	N
What is your financial solidity?	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from Assets and Owner equity (from Economic data)
How many months a year does your cashflow for the business cause significant problems?	Y	N	N
Farm resilience			
What % of your non-forage animal feed is produced on-farm according to energy content (MJ)?*	Y	Y	N
Have you noticed changes in the productivity of your animals with the increased effects of climate change? (e.g., heat waves, floods, change in rainfall periods, etc)*	Y	Y	N
If yes, what changes have you observed?*	Y	N	N
If you have noticed changes in productivity, have you made changes in management practices to mitigate the impacts of climate change in your farm?*	Y	Y	N
If yes, what changes have you made?*	Y	N	N
Is there a specific reason why you don't use by-products, co-products or any other residual streams as animal feeds?*	Y	N	N
If you were a policy-maker, what actions would you implement to make the livestock sector more resilient to climate change?*	Y	N	N
Have you been able to carry out the investment you would like?	Y	Y	N
Excluding 1-off capital items like loans or machinery/building purchase, how much variation is there in your profit margin from year to year?	Y	Y	N
What % of net farm income comes from subsidies?	Auto-calculated	N	Calculated from Total income and Income from subsidies (from Economic data)
How many sources of farm income do you have?	Y	Y	N
How many sources of income come from beyond the farm gate (e.g. not part of the farming business)?	Y	N	N
How satisfied are you with financial support you receive for farming organically?*	Y	N	N
How satisfied are you with your access to country specific central government subsidised advice and or guidance on organic topics?	Y	N	N

Do you measure data on your business and its performance, covering financial accounts but also agronomic measurements and natural capital (e.g. soil resources)?	Y	Y	N
Do you measure and monitor the data you collect?*	Y	Y	N
Do you utilise the data you collect for your business planning and decisions?*	Y	Y	N
How often do you review the state of your business?	Y	Y	N
How is your farm doing?	Y	Y	N
Do you expect to still be in business next year?	Y	Y	N
Do you expect your farm to still be farmed in the next decade?	Y	Y	N
How satisfied are you with your current approach to farm management?	Y	Y	N
Does your innovation make you more resilient to economic shocks (such as price increases, supply shortages, potential future taxes etc)?*	Y	Y	N
Flexibility			
How flexible are you in your choice of inputs and input suppliers?	Y	Y	N
How flexible are you in your choice and number of outputs/services?	Y	Y	N
What % of regular purchases for your farm are from local (< 10miles / < 16km) suppliers or local contractors?	Y	Y	N
Do you carry out benchmarking activities to compare your performance to that of similar farms?	Y	Y	N
Do you have a succession plan? (i.e. a plan for the person(s) who is going to take over the farm)	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade offs for this spur.*	N	N	N

Animal health & welfare

This spur only appears if the farm assessed has livestock.

Table 14. Questions in the Animal health & Welfare spur. * denotes questions with dependencies

Activity and Question	Compulsory ?	Scored ?	Used in calculations?
Staff resources			
Number of labour units (FTEs) looking after livestock (per livestock type)?	Y	Y	Calculated based on nr animals and standard staff resources data ⁷ for livestock type
How often per day are livestock inspected for signs of illness/injury?	Y	Y	N
Are your stock-people trained?	Y	Y	N
How are feed rations for livestock derived?	Y	Y	N
Health plan			
Do you have a health plan?	Y	Y	N
Was your vet/external consultant involved in drawing it up?*	Y	Y	N
Animal health			
How are you working with animal health?	Y	Y	N
Do you cooperate with some external, such as a veterinarian or advisor in preventive animal health?	Y	Y	N
How much do you spend on preventative veterinary medicines (i.e. vaccinations, discussions with vet regarding improving management)?	Y	N	N
How much do you spend on conventional veterinary treatments?	Y	N	N
How much do you spend on alternative veterinary treatments?	Y	N	N
How much do you spend in total on veterinary medicines?	Y	Y	Used to calculate spend per LU based on type and nr of animals
What is the average productive life span (years) of your livestock?	Y	N	N
What is the average productive life span (months) of your livestock?	Y	N	N
How would you describe the mortality/culling rates on your farm?	Y	Y	N
How would you describe lameness incidence in your animals?	Y	Y	N
What management methods do you use to reduce parasite burdens while minimising the use of anthelmintics?	Y	Y	N
How would you describe mastitis incidence in your herd?	Y	Y	N
If you have dairy cows or sheep, how high is the somatic cell counts in delivered milk during the specific year?	Y	Y	N
What is the mortality rate in your growing animals?	Y	Y	N
What is the mortality rate in your adult animals?	Y	Y	N

⁷ Nix, J. (2010) Farm Management Pocketbook, 40th Edition, The Anderson Centre, ISBN: 0-9541201-8-3

What proportion of your animals are not accepted at the abattoir inspection due to pathologies/lesions/drug residues?	Y	Y	N
Animals dead at farm, have they been actively put down or passed away by themselves?	Y	Y	N
Possibility to perform natural behaviours			
Do you restrict grazing/outdoor access at certain times of year (for any species)?	Y	Y	N
How much access do they have to grazing/outdoors on a daily basis during times of year when they are not kept in?	Y	Y	N
How do you judge your animals' ability to perform natural feeding behaviours?	Y	Y	N
How do you judge your animals' ability to perform natural resting behaviours?	Y	Y	N
How do you judge your animals' ability to perform appropriate natural social behaviours?	Y	Y	N
Do housed animals have access to outdoor areas?	Y	Y	N
Do you provide any environmental enrichment (pecking material etc.)?	Y	Y	N
If you have pigs, are your sows fixated around parturition?*	Y	Y	N
Is there any evidence of injurious behaviour? (e.g. feather pecking in poultry, tail biting in pigs, aggression between cattle)	Y	Y	N
How long are calves kept with their dams?*	Y	Y	N
What is the predominant reason for separation?*	Y	N	N
What type of social grouping are dairy calves typically kept in until weaning age (typically 6 months for cattle)?*	Y	Y	N
At what age do you wean your cattle?*	Y	N	N
At what age do you wean your sheep and goats?*	Y	N	N
At what age do you wean your pigs?*	Y	N	N
Housing			
Do housed animals have access to straw or other litter?	Y	Y	N
Do housed animals have access to solid floor?	Y	Y	N
Space available per growing animal	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from average liveweight and number of growing animals and available area for growing animals
Average liveweight per growing animal	Y	N	Used to calculate space available for growing animals
Number of growing animals in the group	Y	N	
Available area for growing animals	Y	N	
Space available per adult animal	Auto-calculated	Y	Calculated from average liveweight and number of adult animals and available area for adult animals
Average liveweight per adult animal	Y	N	Used to calculate space available for growing animals
Number of adult animals in the group	Y	N	
Available area for adult animals	Y	N	
How would you describe the housing/grazing options available to your livestock?	Y	Y	N

How is the housing designed?	Y	Y	N
Are feed and water positioned to minimise the risk of contamination?	Y	Y	N
Do you have organic certification or any country specific recognised animal welfare certification?	Y	Y	N
Biosecurity			
Do you have a biosecurity plan and disease control measures in place?	Y	Y	N
Are new animals entering the farm kept in a separate barn/section?*	Y	Y	N
How do you deal with new livestock coming on to your farm?	Y	Y	N
Innovation-related benefits and trade offs*			
Specify any innovation-related benefits and trade-offs for this spur.*	N	N	N

Part 3

Step by Step guide to using the tool

Go to: https://www.mvarc.eu/tools/dev/re-livestock_tool/

ORIENTATION

NAME OF ASSESSMENT CLONE ASSESSMENT ADD NEW ASSESSMENT

EDIT NAME DELETE ASSESSMENT

LANGUAGE OPTIONS UPLOAD PREVIOUS ASSESSMENT (.json file) DOWNLOAD CURRENT ASSESSMENT (.json file)

A NOTE ON DEPENDENCIES

The full assessment contains over 300 questions. To reduce the burden on farmers filling out the assessment, irrelevant sections and questions are filtered out, depending on the type of farm. Many of these 'dependencies' are related to data that are added to the initial data page, especially the question on farming system:

Q1.0.6 "Farming System?"

→ "Indoor only/landless" – Only the spurs Water Management, Fertiliser Management, Energy and Carbon, Food Security, Agricultural Systems Diversity, Social Capital, Economic data and Farm Business Resilience are shown and need to be completed.

→ "Includes land" – The spurs relating to land management are now also shown - Soil Management, Agri-environmental Management, Landscape & Heritage Features, NPK Budget. If livestock are added in Section 1.6, the Animal Health & Welfare spur will also become live.

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ORIENTATION

EACH CIRCLE CORRESPONDS TO A SPUR – CLICK ON EACH TO FILL OUT THE QUESTIONS

START HERE - INITIAL DATA COLLECTION

Re-Livestock Tool

Assessment Boundaries

The assessment collects information over a 12-month period which can be a calendar year, a financial year or from harvest to harvest. It is important data is collected over the same period each year.
Information collected is restricted to the farmgate (i.e. products entering or leaving the farm) and the farm business (e.g. if land is

% OF COMPULSORY QUESTIONS COMPLETED IN THIS SPUR

SOME CATEGORIES HAVE NO QUESTIONS TO COMPLETE AND ARE CALCULATED FROM DATA ENTERED ELSEWHERE

SCORES FOR SPUR ON A SCALE OF 1 TO 5

RESULTS PAGE

ASSESSMENT FORMAT

WHEN YOU DOWNLOAD THE ASSESSMENT, IT IS SAVED ON YOUR COMPUTER AS A .JSON FILE

.JSON FILE VIEWED IN Notepad ++

- The RE-LIVESTOCK Tool stores your data as a .json file that is downloaded to your computer.
- A JSON file stores simple data structures and objects in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, which is a standard data interchange format.
- It is primarily used for transmitting data between (web) applications.
- JSON files are lightweight, text-based, human-readable, and can be edited using a text editor (e.g. Notepad ++).
- The most important point to note is that only you have the data file and **nothing is stored on the website or internet**.
- Best practice is to **download the file regularly as you work through the assessment**, to ensure you don't lose any of the information you have inputted. Each time you press to download, it downloads to your computer with a new number so you will end up having multiple copies in your download folder.
- When you finish the assessment, or if you get part way through and need to come back to it again to complete, save it somewhere you can find it again!
- Upload the file to carry on working on it, or to make a clone as a starting point for updating for the following year.

STARTING A NEW ASSESSMENT

Go to https://www.mvarc.eu/tools/dev/re-livestock_tool

- Edit name of assessment

1. Click on Pencil to edit

2. Rename e.g. Farm Name and Year of Assessment

3. Save

- Remember to download the file now and then as you work through the assessment.

A NEW ASSESSMENT

- Start filling out the questions in the initial data collection. The data here feeds into other calculations so this is the best place to start.

- Some questions contain drop-down lists to choose from. Others require data to be added.

- Where you need to add extra lines (e.g. to add more crop or livestock types), click on 'Add row'.

- If you need to remove lines, click on the cross.

- Move through the Spurs, answering the questions.

- As you complete a Spur, click on 'Update Score' to see the score.

- When you have completed all Spurs and have updated the scores, check out the Scores page.

- This gives an overview of scores on a radar diagram as well as a break down of scores within activities in each Spur.

ERROR MESSAGES

- Where questions are dependent on answers to other questions, an error message may pop up if the answer is missing.
- Click on the question number to move to the missing question and fill in an answer. If you left an answer requiring a number blank, you may need to add a zero instead.

WHEN YOU HAVE FINISHED.....

- When you have completed the assessment, remember to download the final version, and save it somewhere safe.
- You can then close the assessment.
- When you have completed all of your assessments, please save the JSON files on the Re-Livestock SACO file storage system:

TO CONTINUE FILLING A PART-COMPLETED ASSESSMENT

- If you get part way through the assessment but can't complete it, download the part-completed assessment and save it somewhere safe.
- Next time you want to work on it, click to upload the .json file.

- Choose 'Yes' (otherwise the blank assessment gets included the .json file).

- Carry on completing the file, downloading versions as you work through, and a final version when you have completed it all. Save it somewhere safe - you may need to overwrite the earlier incomplete version.

TO CLONE THE ASSESSMENT TO USE AS A STARTING POINT FOR ANOTHER ASSESSMENT

- If you want to use a previous year's assessment as a starting point for a new year, upload the file as before.

- Then make a copy.

- Rename and save.

- Now when you download the .json file it will contain your previous and your current assessment.

Re-Livestock Tool Tips

On-line access. You will need access to the internet to complete the assessment. If the farmer doesn't have the internet or you can't access their Wi-Fi, consider taking a mobile hotspot with you.

'Incognito' mode. If you are having problems with disappearing spurs, try using the tool in 'incognito mode'. Open a new 'Incognito window' in your browser and then go to the tool. Shortcut: Cntrl Shift N

Emptying the cache. As there have been recent updates to the tool content, if you are not using the tool in Incognito mode, you may need to clear your browsing history to use the latest version. If you use Chrome, go to the three vertical dots in the top right and in the drop down, select 'Clear browsing history'. Then select 'Cached images and files' and confirm to Clear data.

Zoom out to see Tables. When working with tables, on smaller screens, you will need to scroll across or down to see all columns or rows. If this is annoying, an alternative is to 'zoom out' to reduce the size of the text and fields. I found at between 70-80% zoom level, it was still possible to read the text and all columns and rows were visible. Shortcut: Cntrl +/-

Compulsory questions.

The questions where you are required to enter data are marked with a red asterisk (*). These are compulsory as the data are important for feeding into calculations (e.g. nutrient or energy balances) or are used for scoring. e.g. the following question under "Farm Business Resilience" is compulsory:

13.0.14 Do you feel like you receive a fair price for your products? *

However, there are some parts of the tool which are optional or non-compulsory - these questions do not have a red asterisk. These data are usually sensitive data that farmers are sometimes unwilling to share, for example in **Economic data**. So, if the farmers are unable to provide this information, you can leave these questions blank. Of course, we would like to collect this information, as we find that farmers find this information useful in the feedback workshops (e.g. to "benchmark" their performance) and it would be useful for the analyses planned in T5.3. But it is too difficult, for any reason, then it is ok to leave it empty. All questions **without a red asterisk are non-compulsory**, e.g. the following question re: Employment, under "Social Capital":

Employment

How many staff do you employ? (including yourself) ?

11.0.0	Casual (combined total hours of all casual staff)	<input type="text"/>	hours per year
11.0.1	Long term (excluding family) ?	<input type="text"/>	full time equivalent
11.0.2	Family labour ?	<input type="text"/>	full time equivalent

When clicking in the progress percentage under the spur wheels, it will take you to the next unanswered compulsory question.

5. Water Management 7. Fertiliser management 8. Energy and Carbon 9. Food Security 10. Agriculture diversity

0% complete Scores: - 0% complete Scores: - 0% complete Scores: - 0% complete Scores: - 0% complete Scores: -

7.2.13 What is the condition of the floor for your slurry storage system? *

Categories not scoring? Click on the 'Update Score' button.

Where questions are dependent on answers to other questions, an error message may pop up in the top left of the screen if the answer is missing. Click on the question number to move to the missing question and fill in an answer. If you left an answer requiring a number blank, you may need to add a zero instead. Then click to 'Update score' again.

Animal Health & Welfare X
An answer to the question 14.2.6 is needed.

Animal Health & Welfare X
An answer to the question 14.2.7 is needed.

1. Initial data 2. Soil 3. Agri-environmental 4. Landscape and 5. Water management 6. NPK budget 7. Fertiliser management

100% complete no scoring 100% complete Scores: 3.67 100% complete Scores: 3.56 100% complete Scores: 3.25 100% complete Scores: 5 Automatically filled Scores: 3 100% complete Scores: 3

Scoring information. When clicking in a spur / indicator / question number it will show a little tooltip with information regarding whether it is scored or not, and which elements are contributing to the scoring function.

The ‘Comment’ bubble is your friend! While we have tried hard to account for different farm types, inevitably you will come across situations that don’t seem to fit the questions. Don’t worry too much – pick the answer that seems the closest fit and then add any details to the comment bubble associated with the question. We will see those comments when we analysis the data.

Interpreting the results

When the assessment has been completed and the scores updated:

1. Check out the radar diagram on the Scores page
2. Review each spur on the radar diagram, reviewing the 1-5 scores with the farmer, starting with Soil Management and working clockwise
3. A general principle is that a score of 3 would reflect an average performance, less than 3 would be below average and above 3 would be above average.
4. Review the indicator scores bar chart to identify reasons for better or worse performance in a given area. This gives insights into underlying reasons why a farm may have received a better or worse score.
5. Take time to discuss the results with the farmers and explore reasons for better/worse scores.
6. After reviewing the scores, review key indicators, such as the NPK balance. Keep in mind that this is a farm-gate balance (Figure 6. Nutrient cycling within the farm (e.g. applying manure from the farm's livestock onto the farm's arable fields) is therefore not captured; only nutrients entering or leaving the farm.

Farm gate nutrient balance –an overview

Figure 6. Farm gate nutrient balance – an overview

Review overall NPK balance per hectare (ha) to identify potential excesses or losses of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium from the farm system (Figure 7).

Nutrient balance						
Nitrogen kg/ha 0-50 kg/ha 50-70 kg/ha 70-90 kg/ha 90-110 kg/ha 110-130 kg/ha plus+	Sustainability Excellent - Very Good Very Good - Good Good - Average Average - Poor Poor - very poor	Phosphorus and Potassium kg/ha Surplus/deficit less than 5 kg/ha Surplus/deficit of greater than 5kg/ha, less than 10kg/ha Surplus/deficit of greater than 10 kg/ha	Sustainability Very good - Excellent Average - Good Poor - very poor			
Farm gate NPK budget in kg						
	IN	OUT	Balance	Ratio OUT:IN	Balance per ha	Sustainability
N	6.00 6437 kg	6.03 5056 kg	6.09 1381 kg	6.06 1 : 1	6.012 18 kg/ha	6.013 Excellent - Very Good
P	6.01 35 kg	6.04 608 kg	6.010 -573 kg	6.07 18 : 1	6.014 -8 kg/ha	6.015 Average - Good
K	6.02 847 kg	6.05 2296 kg	6.011 -1448 kg	6.08 3 : 1	6.016 -19 kg/ha	6.017 Poor - Very poor

Figure 7. Overall NPK balance per hectare (ha)

Look at the detailed breakdown of inputs and outputs of NPK entering or leaving the farm to identify where potential imbalances occur (Figure 8).

Livestock products - NPK Balance in kg						
Using info from: Initial data 1.6.45, Initial data 1.6.47, Initial data 1.6.48						
1.6.45 Livestock product	1.6.47 Import	1.6.48 Export	6.131 N - OUT	6.133 P - OUT	6.135 K - OUT	
Cow milk (1000s of litres)	0	300	1650 kg	300 kg	450 kg	
Total			1650 kg	300 kg	450 kg	

Figure 8. Key NPK Outputs and Inputs

7. Key indicator: Energy use efficiency. Farmers often find it interesting to review their energy use performance per enterprise and source type to industry standards (Figure 9).

Benchmark comparison ?

	Total energy	Total energy per unit	Standard industry benchmark	% of benchmark
Arable, incorporating horticulture and vegetable production	8.0.22 1900 MJ	8.0.23 27,14 MJ/ha	8.0.24 6 836 MJ/ha	8.0.25 0,4 %
Beef cattle and Sheep	8.0.26 0 MJ	8.0.27 0 MJ/head	8.0.28 546 MJ/head	8.0.29 0 %
Dairy cattle	8.0.30 2 115,98 MJ	8.0.31 21,16 MJ/head	8.0.32 3 721 MJ/head	8.0.33 0,57 %
Pig	8.0.34 -	8.0.35 -	8.0.36 -	8.0.37 -
Poultry - Layers	8.0.38 -	8.0.39 -	8.0.40 -	8.0.41 -
Poultry - Broilers	8.0.42 -	8.0.43 -	8.0.44 -	8.0.45 -

Figure 9. Energy benchmark comparison of farm energy use with industry standards.

8. Key indicator: Economic performance. Review overall Net Farm Income. This is calculated as income minus costs and can indicate whether the farm is making a profit or loss (Figure 10).

12.4 Key figures

12.4.0 Farm Net Income automatically filled

58700 €

Figure 10. Farm Net Income

Review key cost categories and their impact (Figure 11).

12.1.51 Labour costs (not including salary to owners) Please include all costs relating to employment including insurance

25000 €

12.1.52 Machinery costs (including rental and maintenance)

1000 €

12.1.53 Farming overheads (upkeep of land and buildings, including energy, water and administration costs)

4000 €

12.1.54 Rents paid

0 €

12.1.55 Depreciation

2500 €

Figure 11. Key cost categories

Review key sources of income (Figure 10).

Livestock sales Using info from: [Initial data 1.6.0](#)

1.6.0 Livestock 12.0.0 Sales of livestock ?

Dairy Cow	15000	€
Dairy cull calf 0-3 months	1200	€
Suckler cow	1200	€

Livestock products sales Using info from: [Initial data 1.6.25](#)

1.6.25 Livestock product 12.0.1 Annual sales of livestock products ?

Cow milk (1000s of litres)	80000	€
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Figure 12. Income from livestock and livestock products

9. Other indicators that may be of interest when discussing results with farmers:
- Summary of land-use (Initial Data page)
 - Labour use (Social Capital page)
 - Health planning and animal health data (Animal Welfare page)
 - Local food sales (Social Capital page)
 - Livestock and crop diversity (Agricultural Systems Diversity)

Comparing assessments

The tool enables you to compare multiple assessments; this function can be used in many ways, for example, to compare the same farm over several years, or different farms within a region or an innovation case study, or to test the impacts of different scenarios, for example, a change in management or a reduction in livestock numbers.

1. First, upload the assessment JSONs. You will need at least two assessments uploaded to carry out a comparison. Remember, when opening each JSON, to select 'No' when asked if you want to replace the existing assessments, as you want them all open at the same time. You can then 'Save' and download a new JSON that now contains all of the assessments in a single file.

2. Once you have opened all the assessments that you want to compare, go to 'Compare' in the top right of the screen.

- Three assessments are uploaded.

- Select 'Compare' in the top right corner.

3. On the Comparison Dashboard, first select the assessments you want to compare, then click on 'Compare'.

- Select the assessments you want to compare.

- Click on 'Compare'.

- The spur scores from all selected farms are presented together on a radar diagram and the activity scores and selected data are presented for each spur. You can explore these one by one or unfold all charts at the same time.

- Click to 'Unfold all charts'.
- Click on spurs to unfold individually.

Some examples of the data shown in the different spurs:

- It is possible to download the individual charts as .png files by clicking on the disc icon. From these you can compile reports and summaries of the most relevant results.

- Click to download a png file of the chart.

- Compare against a case study average.
As part of the Re-Livestock project, assessments were carried out within eight innovation case studies. See <https://re-livestock.eu/case-studies/> for more details about the individual case studies. From these assessments, the mean spur and activity scores were calculated and can be incorporated into the comparison. Simply select the case study of interest from the dropdown list on the left of the Comparison Dashboard and click on 'Compare'.

- Select Case Study from the dropdown list and click on 'Compare'.

7. The case study average is then added to the radar diagram and to the spur and indicator scores in each Spur breakdown.

Creating datasets from multiple assessments

To make it easier to combine multiple assessments in a single file for subsequent analysis, the tool enables you to create a single dataset, with options to select the Answer values (either as the answer text itself or its corresponding code), the Type of dataset (either CSV or JSON) and the Question IDs being in either the first column or first row (for CSV files only). Choose the JSONs that you want to combine and then select 'Create dataset'. The file will then be downloaded onto your computer.

- Select 'Create dataset'.

- Select the JSONs that you want to combine.

- Select the settings you want for your combined file, then 'Create dataset'. The file will be downloaded to your computer.